

Pseudo-urethanes. Part I.

BY

HEMENDRA KUMAR SEN AND CHITTARANJAN BARAT.

Some observations by one of us (Sen, Physics-Chemistry Colloquium, University College of Science, Calcutta, August, 1924, *Proceedings of the 12th Indian Science Congress*, Benares, 1925, p. 113) relating to the mechanism of the pyruvic acid theory of alcoholic fermentation* have assumed more than speculative importance since

* Sen's scheme of alcoholic fermentation.

Graaff and Le Fevre's scheme based upon bacterial fermentation (*Bact. coli.* and *Bact. typhus* being employed) :-

The amylene oxide structure given to glucose and fructose by Charlton, Haworth and Peat (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129, 89) lends itself also equally easily to convenient transformations by reductase according to the scheme mentioned above.

the publication of a fundamentally similar theory in February 1925 (*Biochem. Zeit.*, 155, 313) by Graaff and Le Fevre, who likewise regard the existence of an intermediate oxide in alcoholic fermentation as extremely probable.

The behaviour of the reductase in yeast, therefore, came to be critically examined with regard to its action on various types of compounds, as it is necessary for the validity of the oxide theory, suggested by one of us, that the reductase should be a sort of general reducing agent, capable of bringing about the reduction of ethers. When one notices that the double bond between carbon and oxygen in aldehydes and ketones is prone to reduction by yeast, though no ethylenic linkage is yet known to have undergone similar change under like conditions, the question of configuration forces itself upon us. Some negative results obtained with chloral acetophenone, $\text{CCl}_3\text{CH}(\text{OH})\text{CH}_2\text{COC}_6\text{H}_5$, in the course of this investigation establish the influence of configuration in such reductions, as chloral and acetophenone are already known to be susceptible of reduction by yeast. Further, the experiment leads to the very important conclusion that the yeast organism is less powerful as a dehydrating agent than the human organism which, according to Tappeiner (*Arch. exp. Path. und Pharm.*, 1894, 33, 264) causes it to lose its aldol phase, giving rise to trichlor-ethyldene acetophenone which is ineffective as a hypnotic. The behaviour of yeast towards hydracetylacetone, $\text{CH}_3\text{CH}(\text{OH})\text{CH}_2\text{COCH}_3$, and diacetone,

has, however, been found different, both undergoing splitting up or partial dehydration passing into ethyldene

acetone and mesityl oxide respectively. This decided stability of the aldol phase in chloralacetophenone and its homologues gave rise to the expectation that probably they would give formamide derivatives (urethanes) of modified hypnotic property. But although intermediate formamide derivatives have been isolated, as is described in the following pages, their constitution as simple urethane derivatives has come to be regarded with doubt for the reasons below.

Chloralacetophenone, when treated with an excess of chloroformamide, yields almost quantitatively a compound of the same composition as

On crystallisation from hot absolute alcohol, the melting point diminishes steadily until it reaches a minimum. This product of minimum melting point was found to contain no nitrogen and to be trichlorethylidene acetophenone, $\text{CCl}_3 \cdot \text{CH} = \text{CH} \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, obtained by Königs by the action of cold concentrated sulphuric acid upon chloral acetophenone (*Ber.*, 1892, 25, 797). The true urethanes are stable in alcoholic solution, and they react with excess of chloroformamide so as to give rise to allophanic esters, thus:—

Thus, contrary to expectation, neither chloralacetophenone nor the supposed urethane derivative (I) gave any allophanic ester even with considerable excess of chloroformamide; nor did benzaldehyde react with the chloroformamide compound of

chloralacetophenone to yield benzylidene diurethanes of the type--

indicating the probable absence of a free NH_2 group. The conjecture, therefore, is that the supposed urethane (I) is a pseudo-urethane, having a metoxazine constitution (II).

The action of chloroformamide was tried further on chloralacetone, chloralacetotoluene, chloral acetophenone and chloral acetoveratrone, and in each case, corresponding pseudo-urethanes were obtained, which upon heating with alcohol, gave trichlorethylidene derivatives, identical with those obtained by the action of concentrated sulphuric acid upon the chloral condensation products. These pseudo-urethanes decompose on melting, forming trichlorethylidene compounds, with the evolution of ammonia and carbon dioxide.

The investigation was extended, as already mentioned, to other compounds having similar aldol phase, *e.g.*, to hydracetylacetone and diacetone. These substances do not yield urethanes with chloroformamide, but readily form the ethylidene compounds by loss of the aldol phase, chloroformamide serving as a dehydrating agent. Thus from hydracetylacetone and diacetone, ethylidene acetone and mesityl oxide respectively were obtained.

It appears, therefore, that the CCl_3CHO group imparts a degree of stability to the aldol phase not met with in diacetone or hydracetyl acetone, and in fact on attempting to prepare benzaldehyde-acetophenone, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}(\text{OH})\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, with glacial acetic acid as the condensing agent, benzylidene acetophenone was obtained, although with chloral under similar conditions, products with the aldol phase were uniformly isolated.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Chloralacetophenone and Chloroformamide.

Chloralacetophenone, $\text{CCl}_3\cdot\text{CH}(\text{OH})\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{CO}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, was prepared according to the method of Königs (*loc. cit.*) by condensing chloral (freshly distilled) with acetophenone in the presence of glacial acetic acid. Nineteen g. of the crude condensation product were obtained from 19 g. of acetophenone. It was best purified from hot petroleum ether, using animal charcoal as a decoloriser; m. p. $68\text{--}70^\circ$. When this was treated with the molecular quantity of chloroformamide in dry ethereal solution, the product obtained was a mixture of the pseudo-urethane derivative and the unconverted chloral acetophenone. In order to effect a complete conversion, an excess of chloroformamide has to be employed, which is not prejudicial to the purity of the condensation product, as no allophanic ester is formed (*loc. cit.*). On mixing the ethereal solutions of chloroformamide and chloralacetophenone, no change of temperature was noticed; the mixture was allowed to stand about 15 minutes at room temperature, and then the ether was boiled off, the excess of chloroformamide decomposed with ice-water, and the pseudo-urethane obtained as a solid, insoluble in water. It can be crystallised by dissolving in *warm* methyl or ethyl alcohol and diluting with water, when it

separates as small prisms, m. p. 155° with decomposition. (Found: N=4.7; Cl=33.98. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3NCl_3$ requires N=4.5; Cl=34.3 per cent.).

The pseudo-urethane on being boiled with absolute alcohol for 2 hours, separates on addition of water as very pale yellow crystals melting at 102° which was found to be identical with trichlorethylidene acetophenone, prepared by the dehydration of chloral acetophenone; a mixture of the two melted at 102° . (Found: Cl=42.66. $C_{10}H_7OC_3$ requires Cl=42.7 per cent.).

The pseudourethane derivative with benzaldehyde and a drop of concentrated hydrochloric acid did not yield the benzylidene diurethane, although under similar conditions the formamide derivatives of both unsymmetrical and symmetrical dichlorisopropyl alcohol gave the corresponding diurethanes.*

Chloralacetotoluene.

Chloralacetotoluene, $CCl_3CH(OH)CH_2.CO.C_6H_4.CH_3$ was obtained from *p*-tolyl methyl ketone (7 g.) by condensation with chloral (8 g.) in the presence of glacial acetic acid (8 g.), in the same manner as chloral acetophenone. The heating on the sand-bath was continued for 15 hours, with a calcium chloride guard tube on the reflux condenser. The yield of crude chloral acetotoluene was about 7 g. It was purified by crystallisation from hot petroleum ether; yield 4 g; m. p. 100° . (Found: Cl=37.4. $C_{11}H_{11}O_2Cl_3$ requires Cl=37.8 per cent.)

The *pseudo-urethane* was prepared by treating an ethereal solution of chloral acetotoluene with an excess

* Benzylidene diurethane of unsymmetrical dichlorisopropyl alcohol m.p. $135-36^{\circ}$. (Found: N=6.5; Cl=32.71. $C_{12}H_{14}O_2N_2Cl_2$ requires N=6.48; Cl=32.87 per cent.).

Benzylidene diurethane of symmetrical dichlorisopropyl alcohol, m.p. $160-162^{\circ}$. (Found: N=6.71; Cl=32.83. $C_{12}H_{14}O_2N_2Cl_2$ requires N=6.48; Cl=32.87 per cent.).

of an ethereal solution of chloroformamide as described before, m.p. 160° with decomposition. (Found: Cl=32.4; N=4.4. $C_{12}H_{13}O_3NCl_3$ requires Cl=32.50; N=4.3 per cent.).

Upon boiling the pseudo-urethane with absolute alcohol for 3 hours under a reflux condenser, a yellowish solid was obtained which on crystallisation melted at $88-90^{\circ}$. The trichlorethylidene acetotoluene prepared by the dehydrating action of sulphuric acid on chloralacetotoluene melted also at $88-90^{\circ}$ and so did a mixture of the two. (Found: Cl=40.05. $C_{11}H_9OCl_3$ requires Cl=40.4 per cent.).

Chloralacetonephthone, $CCl_3.CH(OH).CH_2.CO.C_{10}H_7$ was prepared as before from α -acetonephthone and chloral. The yield of α -acetonephthone was very poor on following the method of Pampel and Schmidt (*Ber.*, 1886, 19, 2898). It was therefore ultimately prepared by the method of Claus and Feist (*Ber.*, 1886, 19, 3180) with an yield of 45 per cent. of the theory. The redistilled acetonephthone (13.5 g.) was mixed with chloral (12 g.) and glacial acetic acid (12 g.), and the mixture was heated under a reflux condenser on the sand-bath for 18 hours. The resulting dark oil was repeatedly washed with hot water to remove chloral and acetic acid and the residue was dissolved in ether. The solution was dried by means of ignited sodium sulphate and filtered. The ether having been evaporated, the oily residue, was stirred with petroleum ether and the petroleum ether extract decanted. On continuing this operation several times, a brown solid weighing about 10 g. was left behind. The substance is very soluble in alcohol and was therefore purified by crystallisation from hot benzene, using animal charcoal as a decoloriser. After two recrystallisations the product was sufficiently pure, m.p. $90-92^{\circ}$. (Found: Cl=33.08. $C_{14}H_{11}O_2Cl_3$ requires Cl=33.54 per cent.)

Upon treatment with chloroformamide as usual, it gives a pseudo-urethane, m. p. 125° with decomposition. (Found: N=4.04; Cl=29.73. $C_{15}H_{12}O_3NCl_3$ requires N=3.88; Cl=29.54 per cent.)

On refluxing the compound with absolute alcohol for 2 hours, the trichlorethylidene acetonephthone was obtained as a yellowish substance, m. p. $105-106^{\circ}$. (Found: Cl=35.17. $C_{14}H_8OCl_3$ requires Cl=35.56 per cent.)

Chloral acetone, $CCl_3CH(OH).CH_2.CO.CH_3$ was prepared according to the method of Königs (*Ber.*, 1892, 25, 794) but the yield was exceedingly poor. By substituting 1 per cent. sodium carbonate solution for sodium hydroxide, the yield was better, but was considerably lower than that claimed by Königs. From 3.2 g. of acetone about 0.5 g. of the pure condensation product, m. p. $75-76^{\circ}$, was obtained. The pseudo-urethane prepared as usual melted at 98° with decomposition. (Found: Cl=42.87. $C_6H_8O_3NCl_3$ requires Cl=42.84 per cent.)

The yield was so poor that no further investigation could be carried out.

Chloralacetoveratrone, $CCl_3.CH(OH).CH_2.CO.C_6H_3(OCH_2)_2$. An attempt was made to prepare veratrol from catechol according to Perkin and Weizmann's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 89, 1649) but without any success whatsoever. Accordingly it was prepared by the method of Marrasse (*Annalen*, 1869, 152, 74) from guaiacol. The yield was very satisfactory, about 35 g. of veratrol being obtained from 36.4 g. of guaiacol. The product boiled at $205-206^{\circ}$.

Acetoveratrone was prepared according to the method of Pictet and Gams (*Ber.*, 1909, 42, 2947). The yield was good. The boiling point, however, was $172-174^{\circ}$ under 15 mm. as against 206° at 12 mm. given by the authors.*

* The melting point, however, was $49-50^{\circ}$ as given by the authors.

On oxidation of the acetoveratrone by alkaline permanganate, veratric acid (m. p. 180°) was obtained which was compared with veratric acid from stock. The semicarbazone melted at $218-20^{\circ}$ with decomposition. (Found: $N = 18.1$. $C_{11}H_{15}O_3N_3$ requires $N = 17.7$ per cent.).

Redistilled acetoveratrone (6 g.) was treated with chloral (5.1 g.) and glacial acetic acid (5.1 g.) and heated for 7 hours. The pasty mass obtained after washing with hot water was purified by repeated washing with petroleum ether; yield 6 g. As the substance is very sparingly soluble in benzine, it was crystallised from dilute alcohol by cooling with ice. The pure product was obtained after three crystallisations, using animal charcoal as decoloriser; yield 3 g., m.p. $120-22^{\circ}$. (Found: $Cl = 32.46$. $C_{12}H_{13}OCl_3$ requires $Cl = 32.2$ per cent.).

Considerable difficulty was experienced in preparing the pseudo-urethane derivative of chloralacetoveratrone. Even with marked excess of chloroformamide the condensation product was impure, melting between 80° and 100° and decomposing at $105-108^{\circ}$. Further investigation is proceeding in this direction.

Action of Chloroformamide on Hydracetyl Acetone.

Hydracetyl acetone, obtained from acetaldehyde and acetone in the presence of dilute potassium carbonate according to the method of Claisen (*Ber.*, 1892, 25, 3164), on being treated with chloroformamide in cold ethereal solution, evolved much hydrochloric acid and heat. The ether being expelled, the residue consisting apparently almost entirely of solid ammonium chloride, was treated with ice water when an oil was left. This was extracted with ether and the ethereal solution dried by ignited sodium sulphate and evaporated. The remaining oil boiled at 122° , the boiling point of ethylidene acetone.

Action of Chloroformamide on Diacetone.

Diacetone, prepared by the condensation of acetone in the presence of calcium hydroxide according to the method of Hoffmann (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 31, 723) and treated as above with chloroformamide, gave an oil, b. p. 130°, which had the characteristic odour of mesityl oxide. A semicarbazone prepared in the usual way, melted at 128°. Mesityl oxide prepared by Freer and Lachmann's process (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1897, 19, 887) gave a semicarbazide, m. p. 126-128°. A mixture of the two melted at 128°, indicating that the two products were identical.

DEPARTMENT OF APPLIED CHEMISTRY,

UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,

CALCUTTA.

Received July 24, 1926.
